

Breeding Ratio Nuclear Data Uncertainty Analysis. Impact of criticality constraint.

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ABSTRACT

Breeding capacity is a key parameter of the business model of advanced Fast Neutron Spectrum reactors. A discrepancy between evaluated and actual nuclear data would trigger a discrepancy between calculated and observed criticality. The operator will compensate this discrepancy to make the reactor critical, probably by a small change in the geometry. Both the initial nuclear data discrepancy and the induced geometry changes would have an impact on the breeding ratio. In this paper we will calculate the associated sensitivity taking into account the k-reset mechanism. The test case is an OECD-NEA UAM benchmark of a pin of Fast Reactor sodium cooled reactor, whose reactivity will be adjusted by the content in fissile Plutonium. An uncertainty analysis is driven, using SCALE 44 G nuclear data covariance. The criticality constraint has a surprisingly small impact on the total uncertainty which stays close to 2.1%. As BR is close to 1, usually smaller than 1.2, such an uncertainty may have strong impact on the fuel cycle scenarios. Because the criticality constraint is changing the intensity and the sign of sensitivities of the most important reactions, the ranking of the most important reactions is completely reordered. The effect of correlations between reactions, somehow associated with error compensation, is also affected.

Keywords: Breeding, Nuclear Data, Uncertainty Analysis, Perturbation Theory

1. INTRODUCTION

Efficient use of natural resources allowed by the recycling of the fissile materials, and reduction of nuclear waste have been driving the development of advanced nuclear reactor since the beginning of the nuclear era. The capacity to “breed” this fissile material is even in the name of the Experimental Breeder Reactor 1 (EPR-1), the reactor said to have been the first whose energy has been used to power a light bulb. If disposed of and not recycled, the Plutonium used in those reactors would be the biggest contributor to long term radiotoxicity after some two hundred years after fuel use, once most of the fission products would have decayed. So, breeding capacity is one of the most important characteristics of fast reactors associated with neutron transport. If Breeding Ratio (BR) is close to one, an uncertainty on this parameter may change the production of fissile material, which may allow for more reactor to be started, into a need for fissile material which would have to be found elsewhere. Thus, breeding ratio have a strong impact on fuel cycle scenario.

Nuclear reactors are kept critical during operation. The uncertainty on actual uncertainty of criticality is zero. Which means that the design of the reactor and its operation procedures are adapted to cope with the existence of calculated uncertainties. By changing the geometry, the mechanism called “k-reset” will itself have an impact on the neutronic parameters such as the Breeding Ratio. In this paper, we will see how the critically constraint changes sensitivity calculation and then impacts the uncertainty analysis.

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2. CRITICALITY CONSTRAINED BREEDING RATIO

2.1. Breeding Ratio Definition and Link with Criticality

Breeding ratio (BR) is defined in equation (1) as the ratio between the production of ^{239}Pu by capture on ^{238}U and the absorption of neutrons by ^{239}Pu .

$$BR = \frac{\Sigma_{capture}^{U^{238}} \phi}{\Sigma_{absorption}^{Pu^{239}} \phi} = \frac{\Sigma_{capture}^{U^{238}} \phi}{\Sigma_{fission}^{Pu^{239}} \phi + \Sigma_{capture}^{Pu^{239}} \phi} \quad (1)$$

It happens that the reactions involved in the definition of BR are also the most important reactions in the definition of criticality as shown in equation (2). In that equation ν is the average neutron fission yield.

$$k_{eff} = \frac{\nu \Sigma_{fission} \phi}{\Sigma_{absorption} \phi + Leakage} = \frac{\nu \Sigma_{fission}^{Pu^{239}} + \nu \Sigma_{fission}^{U^{238}} + \dots}{\Sigma_{fission}^{Pu^{239}} + \Sigma_{capture}^{Pu^{239}} + \Sigma_{capture}^{U^{238}} \phi + \Sigma_{fission} \phi \dots} \quad (2)$$

The fissile absorption, i.e. the denominator of BR definition, is largely dominated by fission, which is the key contributor of the numerator of k_{eff} . Reciprocally, the capture of the fertile, is both a key contributor of the denominator of k_{eff} and of the numerator of BR. Thus, if it happens that uncertainty in the nuclear data have some impact on the BR, it will have also a strong impact on k_{eff} . And if some procedures are applied to keep the reactor critical and neutralize the uncertainty on effective k_{eff} , this procedure will also change important nuclides' concentrations, which will trigger a strong impact on BR.

2.2. Physics of Criticality Constrained Breeding Ratio

If BR is close to one, for each of the ν fission neutrons, more than one will be absorbed by the fissile material and almost the same would be absorbed by the fertile material to breed its replacement. In Water Reactors, keeping the reactor critical is done by adjusting poisons such as boron concentration. During startup procedures of fast reactors, it could be done by adding assemblies, which is an increase of the critical mass in the reactor, and a reduction of leakages. In Molten Salt Reactors, criticality may be adjusted by changing the proportion of fissile to fertile material thanks to online chemical control.

Sylvain David suggested in [1] the approximate formulae (3) for the number of neutrons available per fission in a critical breeder, sometime presented as "the excess number of available neutrons after criticality and breeding are assured". In that formulae, α is the ratio of capture to fission cross-sections of the fissile material. Such a reactor would be critical. For any fissile material absorption, enough absorptions in the fertile material would replace the lost fissile atoms. The assumption is that the distance to criticality would be compensated by the fissile to fertile ratio.

$$Excess\ neutrons\ per\ fission = \nu - 2 \times (1 + \alpha) \quad (3)$$

In this formulae, we see that :

- The neutron fission yield appears as a key parameter, while it is absent from the definition of the BR in Equation (1). The obvious fact that any increase in the neutron fission yields would improve the available number of neutrons do not appear in the BR definition and is corrected here.
- The strong dependance of BR to the capture of the fertile material is expected to be reduced by the criticality constraint.

- The importance of the capture of the fissile material is doubled by the criticality constraint. This comes from the fact that any capture on the fissile is lost for criticality. Each fission would need one neutron, but also, α neutrons captures on the fissile. So for each fission, $(1 + \alpha)$ neutrons are needed. And also $(1 + \alpha)$ fissile atoms would have to be replaced by $(1 + \alpha)$ captures on the fertile material. Which explains the doubling of the importance of the fissile capture cross section. A reaction often under looked.

The formulae was further developed in [2] to include some other minor reactions and tested against direct calculation in [3]. It showed the importance of ^{233}U capture cross section of Thorium Fueled breeders and lead to a still active request in the High Priority Request List [4] of OECD/NEA Data Bank.

2.3. Impact of breeding uncertainty

A Breeding Ratio is one of the most important characteristic of breeder reactor and is usually close to one. As a function of moderation ratio (the share of volume occupied by fuel and coolant), and depending on the use, or not, of axial and or radial blankets, the BR can be adjusted in a rather big range from 0.5 to 1.3 in the most ambitious designs. The most extreme values are very specific, and usually, as a function of the fuel cycle objectives, the designers would propose a value much closer to one, probably between 0.9 and 1.1. If the chosen value is very close to one, then the impact of uncertainty in the range of a few % would make a dramatic change in the scenario study. It may change the sign of the flux of needed fissile material as the reactor could switch from net producer (which could help the startup of new reactor) to net consumer, which would need constant feeding materials and then some dependance on the natural uranium markets .

G. Krivitchik [5] studied the impact of uncertainty in fuel cycle studies. The effect of uncertainties during one irradiation would change the outgoing materials that would become the ingoing material after recycling. It happens that the recycling tends to act as a negative feedback and in many cases, would reduce the impact of uncertainties. The complexity of the propagation of uncertainty during multiple recycling was studied with the use of meta-modeling, themselves based on very few groups neutronics calculation. That study would probably need updates so as to take into account the impact of more recent, very detailed in energy, covariance matrices.

3. CRITICALITY CONSTRAINED SENSITIVITIES RESULTS

Here, the objective is to evaluate the sensitivities and the uncertainty of the change in mass of fissile material with burn-up associated with the uncertainty in Nuclear Data. The quite complex theory of sensitivity calculation with burn-up was proposed in the 80's by Takeda et al. [6] and Williams [7]. Chiba et al. [8], Perfetti et al. [9] or CEA teams ([10] and [11]) proposed recent works developing implementations of this theory in modern codes. In that framework, the constraint of the criticality has been developed by Portinari et al [12] and applied to the very specific case of the High Flux Reactor of Institut Laue Langevin Williams. We know no other implementation of it or application to any other case.

A proxy to the calculation of the actual mass change at the end of irradiation is to look at the Breeding Ratio, ie to look at the instantaneous ratio between creation and disappearance of the nuclide of interest. The impact of the changes in the flux spectrum with burn-up cannot be taken into account but is expected to be limited in the case of fast reactor spectrum. The Sensitivities of ratio of reactions to Nuclear Data are historically calculated using Generalized Perturbation Theory (GPT). Williams [7] proposed the extension of it to take into account the so-called k-reset mechanism used in this paper and briefly introduced in this part.

3.1. K-Reset Mechanism

The sensitivity to the reaction x will be calculated by the summation of three terms presented in Equation (4). In this equation, de "Direct" and "Indirect" terms are the classical ones. The Direct term exists only for the three cases where the x reaction appears in the definition of the BR, for instance the capture of ^{238}U . Any reaction x would have an impact on the flux spectrum that would itself change the reaction rates in the definition of BR in Equation (1). This impact is the Indirect term and can be

calculated using GPT. In deterministic codes, this would be calculated by the classical combination of generalized importance function and reaction rates.

$$S_x^{BR} = \underbrace{\frac{x}{BR} \frac{dBR}{dx}}_{S_{Direct}} + \underbrace{\frac{x}{BR} \frac{dBR}{d\phi} \frac{d\phi}{dx}}_{S_{Indirect}} - \underbrace{\frac{S_{N_c}^{BR}}{S_{N_c}^k}}_{K-reset} S_x^k \quad (4)$$

The principle of the k-reset mechanism is that the change in the x reaction on k_{eff} is compensated by another change in the geometry, for instance the density of a “Control Nuclide”. In our simplified pin cell case coming from the benchmark describe in [13], we will compensate the criticality by the change in the density of the fissile material, i.e. ^{239}Pu . The change in density N_c of the Control Nuclide would change the BR proportionally to the sensitivity of BR to N_c . The last term of Equation (4) shows that the impact of reaction x on BR is then proportional to the sensitivity of k_{eff} to reaction x with a proportionality factor that depend on the ratio of the sensitivities to N_c of BR and k_{eff} . All those sensitivities can be calculated by GPT. Most of Monte Carlo codes now have sensitivity calculation capabilities, implemented via various methods [14].

3.2. Application in Serpent 2

Thanks to the work presented in [15], Serpent 2 allows for the calculation of sensitivities of reaction rate ratios. Unfortunately, the definition of BR shows a denominator that is itself a sum of reactions and Serpent 2 cannot calculate the sensitivities of such complex ratios. Here we use the property shown in equation (6) that the sensitivity of the inverse of a ratio is just the opposite of the ratio to compute the sensitivities of BR. We have then used Serpent 2 to calculate the sensitivities of the inverse of BR whose denominator becomes a single reaction. Technically, by adding the sensitivities of ^{239}Pu capture to ^{238}U capture ratio and ^{239}Pu fission to ^{238}U capture ratio, and changing the sign, we were able to calculate the BR sensitivities.

$$S_x^{BR^{-1}} = \frac{\frac{1}{BR^{-1}} \frac{dBR^{-1}}{dx}}{\frac{dx}{x}} = \frac{-BR \frac{1}{BR^2} \frac{dBR}{dx}}{\frac{dx}{x}} = -S_x^{BR} \quad (6)$$

3.3. Sensitivity Results

Sensitivity results are shown in Table I. Indirect terms, associated with the change in reaction rates due to the spectrum sensitivity to the cross-sections are usually negligible. Then, in the total of the no-k-reset case, direct term are dominant. The k-reset case is very different. First we can see that nubar, the neutron fission yields is having a very strong sensitivity, even stronger than one as it is the case for k_{eff} . Fertile material capture sensitivity is more than halved. Concerning the fissile material, the capture cross section sensitivity is almost double as can be expected by Equation (3). The impact of the criticality constraint on the fissile fission cross section is even stronger. The absolute value is divided by three, and its sign is changed, which will have some importance for the effect of correlations between reactions in the uncertainty analysis.

Table I. Sensitivities of Breeding Ratio to the most important reactions

		Direct	Indirect	k – reset	Tot No-Kreset	Tot K-reset
²³⁸ U	Capture	1.0	8.81×10^{-3}	5.35×10^{-3}	1.01	0.47
	Fission	0	5.46×10^{-3}	0.183	5.46×10^{-3}	0.188
²³⁹ Pu	Capture	0.226	4.75×10^{-2}	-0.1	-0.178	-0.278
	Fission	0.775	3.03×10^{-2}	1.03	-0.744	0.283
	Nubar	0		1.41	0	1.41

Figure 1. Comparison of Sensitivity profiles of BR to ²³⁹Pu cross sections with and without k-reset .

Figure 1 shows the profile of the sensitivities of BR to ²³⁹Pu cross sections with and without k-reset. One can see the important profile changes in amplitude explained before as well as the change in sign of the fission cross section. An interesting feature is that the profiles of fission sensitivity are changed with the k-reset mechanism. This comes from the fact that the effect of this reaction on k_{eff} , i.e. the sensitivity profile of k_{eff} is different from the profile of the reaction rate, which appears in the direct term, which is the dominant one in the classical BR sensitivity. Indeed, the k_{eff} sensitivity is adjoint weighted, when the direct term is not.

4. UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS

The results of the previous sensitivity analysis were combined with the “old” 44 G covariance matrices of SCALE [16]. Those matrices are rather old but, as they were one of the proposed standard sources of the UAM benchmarks of the WPRS of OECD/NEA, they have been one of the most used in the world. It is probable that the most important reactions contributing to the uncertainty in the BR would still be

the same even though the relative importance of each of them and the error compensations coming from the correlations between them, could be very different.

The results is that the total uncertainty (the root of the standard deviation) with or without k-reset is almost not changed and is 2,02% and 2,16%. This may look small, but when compared to the range of most of the BR, ie between 0.9 and 1.1, this is a very strong relative uncertainty.

The details of the contribution of the most important reactions to the total variance are shown in Table II and Table III. It happens that they are the ones seen in the BR definition of Equation (1) or in the excess number of neutrons of Equation (3). To improve the readability of the table, contributions smaller than 0,1% are not written. The most important discrepancies in the share of the variance are the following:

- The neutron fission yield (ν -bar) was not existing and becomes the most important contribution in the variance with the criticality constraint. This correspond to its role in formulae (3)
- The capture cross section of the fertile material, the numerator of the definition of BR, is not anymore the most important one. Nevertheless, it remains of the most important even though the criticality constraint as Equation (3). This shows at the same time both that the trend expected from Equation (3), is valid. And that such simplified formulae are not so accurate.
- The capture cross section of the fissile material contribution becomes almost as big as the one of the fertile material. This is also compatible with Equation (3)

If we neglect the correlation between reactions, and sum only diagonal terms, the total uncertainty would be respectively 2.04 % (previously 2.02%) and 2.09% (previously 2.16%). The effect of correlations would lead to error compensation in the classical case, but to would in fact increase the total uncertainty when the constraint of criticality is applied. This comes from the change in sign of the sensitivity of \bar{X} . More recent covariance data tends to be more complete, so those effect may be reinforced with other nuclear data libraries.

Table II. Share of total variance on the Breeding Ratio from different nuclear reactions, no k-reset.

		²³⁸ U		²³⁹ Pu	
		Capture	Fission	Capture	Fission
²³⁸ U	Capture	94%	0%		
	Fission	0%	0%		
²³⁹ Pu	Capture			6%	-1%
	Fission			-1%	2%

Table III. Share of total variance on the Breeding Ratio from different nuclear reactions, k-reset activated.

		²³⁸ U			²³⁹ Pu		
		Capture	Fission	Nubar	Capture	Fission	Nubar
²³⁸ U	Capture	18%	2%				
	Fission	2%	1%				
	Nubar			7%			
²³⁹ Pu	Capture				15%	1%	
	Fission				1%	7%	
	Nubar						46%

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the k-reset mechanism was applied to take into account the constraint of criticality on the sensitivities. Criticality constrained sensitivity of reaction rate ratios can be obtained by any tool able

to calculate sensitivity of reaction. In this paper we used Serpent 2. We found that, for the reactions contributing to the definition of the BR, the constrained sensitivities are drastically changed: their intensity can be halved or doubled, and their sign changed. Such results are compatible with the physics of the number of excess neutron after criticality. Surprisingly, with the covariance matrices used here, the impact of the criticality constraint is very limited in the total uncertainty which would stay in the range of 2,1%. This is probably very impactful for scenario studies where the objective is usually to be close to one with a small margin. The uncertainty analysis should be redone with more recent covariance data. In particular, the effect of correlations between reactions may be of importance as the change in sign of some sensitivities could make the contribution of the correlations positive and not negative in the total uncertainty.

INFORMATION ABOUT AUTHOR EMPLOYER

Hedi El-Amami is now an employee of CEA Cadarache. The material for this paper was acquired during his time as LPSC-CNRS.

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